

Prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome in Chronic Plaque Psoriasis: A Hospital Based Case Control Study**K. Priyanka¹, A Pramod², K Pratima³, S. Akshay⁴, M. Rahul⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Government Medical College, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Government Medical College, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Government Medical College, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Government Medical College, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Government Medical College, Baramati, Pune, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:

Psoriasis is a papulosquamous, proliferative condition of the skin, in which both genetic and environmental influences have a critical role. Psoriasis with metabolic syndrome causes significant physical and psychological morbidity to the patient. Therefore, the present study was conducted to study prevalence of metabolic syndrome in chronic plaque psoriasis at tertiary care centre. The present study was case control study carried out at Department of Dermatology of tertiary care centre during November 2021 to October 2022. A total of 50 cases of chronic plaque psoriasis diagnosed clinically above 18 years were enrolled while 50 age and sex matched controls were included. Metabolic syndrome is defined based on the revised criteria from NCEP ATP III. The statistical software namely SPSS 22.0 used for the analysis of the data. The mean age in Cases was 40.34±12.50 years and Control was 41.50±13.28 years with no significant difference. Both the group shows male dominance. Percentage of metabolic syndrome in patients with psoriasis in cases (42%) was more as compared to controls (2%) was statistically highly significant (P<0.0001) The present study concludes that there is a significantly higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in psoriasis patients as compared to general population.

Keywords: Metabolic syndrome, Psoriasis, Case-control.

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Introduction

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disease that affects about 3% of the population. [1,2] It is a papulosquamous, proliferative condition of the skin, in which both genetic and environmental influences have a critical role. The disease is enormously variable in duration, periodicity of flares and extent. [3]

Psoriasis can be associated with other diseases, which may have a major impact on patients. The more common comorbidities include psoriatic arthritis and anxiety /depression disorder. [4,5] More recently, psoriasis has also been reported to be associated with metabolic disorders including obesity, dyslipidaemia and diabetes. [6,7]

Metabolic syndrome is a cluster of risk factors including central obesity, atherogenic dyslipidaemia, hypertension and glucose

intolerance, and is a strong predictor of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and stroke. [8,9] The importance of metabolic syndrome is that it may confer a cardiovascular risk higher than the individual components. Men with metabolic syndrome are almost three times more likely to die of coronary artery disease after adjustment for conventional cardiovascular risk factors. [10]

Psoriasis with metabolic syndrome causes significant physical and psychological morbidity to the patient, and is a considerable economic burden to both the patient and health care system, largely associated with medication costs and frequent outpatient visits. There is evidence for an inflammatory basis for diseases such as diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis, dyslipidemia and metabolic syndrome that has stimulated research in examining the risk of these conditions in patients

with systemic inflammatory disorders such as psoriasis.

Therefore, the present undertaken to study prevalence of metabolic syndrome in chronic plaque psoriasis at tertiary care centre.

Objective: To study the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in patients with chronic plaque type of psoriasis

Methodology

The present study was case control study carried out at Department of Dermatology, K.J Somaiya Medical college and research centre November 2021 to October 2022. The study was conducted after obtaining clearance from the Ethical Committee of the institute. A total of 50 cases of chronic plaque psoriasis diagnosed clinically above 18 years were enrolled while 50 age and sex matched controls were enrolled among patients referred for dermatological conditions other than psoriasis were included in the study. Patients receiving any systemic treatment for psoriasis including acitretin, cyclosporine, methotrexate, phototherapy or biologics for at least one month before enrolment were excluded.

After signed informed consent, all subjects were registered and their demographic, biometric and the other relevant data was recorded on a case record form. The cases were subjected to a thorough

history taking with respect to age, sex, marital status, occupation, onset, duration and progression of psoriasis, associated comorbidities (Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, Tuberculosis, Jaundice, Hypercholesterolemia and Epilepsy), history of major medical/surgical disease, history of medications, treatment history, personal history, obstetric and menstrual history in females. A thorough clinical examination was done that included general examination (pulse, BP, weight, height) and dermatological examination which included number, size and distribution of psoriatic plaques, calculation of PASI score,¹² evaluation of oral/ genital, palms/ soles, scalp/ nail involvement and examination of joints.

Patient was advised to follow up for investigations after 12 hrs overnight fasting for blood examination (serum lipid profile, fasting blood sugars). Serum cholesterol and triglycerides were measured with enzymatic calorimetric method. High-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels were measured using a direct immunoassay method. Fasting glucose levels were measured using a glucose oxidase method. Metabolic syndrome is defined based on the revised criteria from NCEP ATP III.¹³ Data was entered in excel sheet and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 22.0. Appropriate test of significance was used wherever necessary. The p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Table 1: Distribution according to age, sex and BMI among patients:

Demographic profile	Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	P value
Mean Age (yrs)	40.34±12.50	41.50±13.28	0.654
Male: Female	34:16	38:12	0.373
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	24.13±03.42	23.99±03.29	0.726

It was seen that mean age in Cases was 40.34±12.50 years and Control was 41.50±13.28 years. There was no significant difference (p=0.654) between the two groups. Amongst cases 34 (68%) were males and 16 (32%) were females. In Control, 38 (76%) were males and 12 (24%) were females. (Table 1)

Table 2: Distribution of Metabolic Syndrome in Cases and Controls:

Metabolic Syndrome	Cases (n=50)		Controls (n=50)		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Present	21	42	01	02	< 0.0001
Absent	29	58	49	98	
Total	50	100	50	100	

The above table shows, amongst cases 21 (42%) were having metabolic syndrome as compared to 1 (2%) patient in controls. Percentage of metabolic syndrome in patients with psoriasis is statistically highly significant in cases as compared to controls. (P<0.0001)

Table 3: Metabolic Syndrome components in Cases and Control Group

Variables		No. of patients (%)		P value
		Cases	Controls	
Increased Waist Circumference	Present	06(12%)	04(8%)	0.781
	Absent	44(88%)	46(92%)	
Hypertension	Present	22(44%)	04(8%)	< 0.0001
	Absent	28(56%)	46(92%)	
Hyperglycemia	Present	28(56%)	9(18%)	< 0.0001
	Absent	22(44%)	41(82%)	
Hypertriglyceridemia	Present	18(36%)	05(10%)	0.002

	Absent	32(64%)	45(90%)	
Low HDL	Present	21(42%)	05(10%)	0.004

The above table shows, metabolic components in cases was more, hypertension (44%), hyperglycemia (56%), hypertriglyceridemia (36%) and low HDL (42%) compared to controls with statistically significant difference. (Table 3).

Table 4: Comparison of PASI Score with Metabolic Syndrome:

PASI	Metabolic Syndrome		P value
	Present (n=21)	Absent (n=29)	
0-10	19 (90.5%)	25(86.2%)	P=0.260
>10-20	02 (9.5%)	02 (6.9%)	
>20-30	0(0%)	02(6.9%)	

The table no 4 shows, majority of PASI score in cases with and without Metabolic syndrome was 0-10 (90.5% vs 86.2%) There was no statistical significance between PASI Score and Metabolic Syndrome with p value= 0.260.

Table 5: Comparison of duration of Psoriasis with Metabolic Syndrome:

Duration of Psoriasis (yrs)	Metabolic Syndrome		P value
	Present (n=21)	Absent (n=29)	
<1	06 (28.6%)	10(34.5%)	P=0.762
1-10	13 (61.9%)	15 (51.7%)	
11-20	02(9.5%)	04(13.8%)	

The table no 5 shows, majority of cases with and without Metabolic syndrome had duration of Psoriasis 1-10 years. (61.9% Vs 51.7%) There was no statistical significance between duration of psoriasis and Metabolic Syndrome with p value= 0.762

Discussion:

The present study the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in patients with chronic plaque type of psoriasis. In present study the mean age at the diagnosis of psoriasis was 40.34±12.50 (years). These findings are not consistent with the studies done by Dogra et al and Bedi. [14,15] Dogra concluded 2nd and 4th decade as common age group for psoriasis, since present study did not include <18 yrs of patients of psoriasis, we did not get 2nd decade as common age group as seen by Dogra et al. [14]

In the present study of 50 psoriasis patients, 34 (68%) were male patients and 16 (32%) were female patients, the male to female sex ratio being 2.12:1. Studies done by Bedi, [15] Asokan et al [16] and Dogra et al [14] show similar findings of male preponderance as in the present study.^{27,98,99}

In present study mean BMI (kg/m²) of cases was 24.13 and that of controls was 23.99 (p value= 0.726), hence there was no significant difference in BMI between the two groups. However, controversy still exists as to whether obesity is a result of psoriasis or a causative factor. Herron et al. [17] found that psoriasis patients were almost twice as likely to be obese compared with the general population (34% vs. 18%; p=0.001). Naldi

et al. [18] identified obesity as an independent risk factor associated with psoriasis, accounting for 16% of all psoriasis cases at onset. Mallbris et al [19] also showed no significant difference in BMI between a psoriatic patient within a year of onset and a matched control suggesting that obesity follows psoriasis.

In present study, according to the revised NCEP ATP III criteria the presence of metabolic syndrome in cases and controls was 21(42%) and 01(02%) respectively (p value <0.0001), which suggest statistically significant correlation between psoriasis and metabolic syndrome. Study done by Nisa N and Qazi MA [20] showed a higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome among psoriatic patients than the controls [28% vs 6%, P<0.05] also the higher prevalence of individual components of metabolic syndrome like triglyceride levels >150 mg/dl(73/150 vs 24/150,p=0.0005), fasting plasma glucose >100mg/dl (27/150 vs 08/150 p= 0.0006) and blood pressure >130/85(74/150 vs 24/150, p=0.0005) in patients of psoriasis than in controls. These findings were consistent with our study.

The study done by Gisondi et al [21] also showed a higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome among psoriatic patients than the controls [30.1% vs 20.6%, P= 0.005]. Also, they found the higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in psoriatic patients than controls after the age of 40 years, these findings were consistent with present study. Furthermore, Sommer et al [22] also found higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome among hospitalized psoriatic patients as compared to hospitalized melanoma patients.

Table 6: Comparison of prevalence of metabolic syndrome and its components in different studies:

	Nisa et al.[20]	Gisondi et al.[21]	Thomas et al.[23]	Malhotra SK et al.[24]	Present study
Comorbidities	Study patient's vs Control Patients %age				
Hypertriglyceridemia	48.6% vs 16%	37.8% vs 23.3%	4.10%	43.3% vs 13.3%	36% vs 10%
Hypertension	49.3% vs 16%	40.8% vs 39.5%	14.10%	46.6% vs 13.3%	44% vs 8%
Low HDL levels	56.6% vs 62.6%	18% vs 21.5%	-	3.3% vs 0%	42% vs 10%
Obesity (BMI)	14.6% vs 20.6%	57.1% vs 47.6%	6.60%	58.3% vs 33.3%	28% vs 34%
Diabetes Mellitus	18% vs 5.3%	19.2% vs 20.9%	11.60%	8.3% vs 3.3%	56% vs 18%
Metabolic Syndrome	28% vs 6%	30.1% vs 20.6%	-	25% vs 3.3%	42% vs 2%

Nisa N and Qazi MA [20] in their study observed longer mean disease duration in psoriatic patients with metabolic syndrome than those without metabolic syndrome. However, in present study there was no association between duration of psoriasis and presence of metabolic syndrome. [23]

Thus, a higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in patients with psoriasis as compared to non-psoriatic patients which could play a relevant role in accelerating atherosclerosis. The association is not limited to severe cases but also occurs with mild cases. The study suggests that all patients with psoriasis should be encouraged to correct aggressively their modifiable cardiovascular risk factors, in particular, metabolic syndrome. [24] Future multicentre studies are indicated on this topic with a larger sample size to validate the findings of this study in an Indian population. Further prospective studies are required to determine the directionality of the association between psoriasis and metabolic syndrome and to study other unexplored confounders including diet, physical activity, alcohol and genetic factors which may be important residual confounders in this relationship.

Conclusion

The present study concludes that there is a significantly higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in psoriasis patients as compared to general population. While managing the psoriatic plaques of these patients, concerns should extend to the atherosclerotic plaques as well.

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